

THE CONSORTIUM_

United in purpose

13 partners

8 countries

The team includes top universities, research institutes, SMEs, and industry leaders, all united by a shared goal of advancing AI-driven software engineering.

Let's build
the future
of software,
together_

Hello world!
We are_
hivemind

Human-centred
collaboratIVE
Multi-ageNt
framework for
accelerating
software
Development
and maintenance

The AI sidekick for real collaboration

HIVEMIND transforms AI from a passive coding assistant into an active collaborator through an LLM-based multi-agent system, supporting developers in automating, optimizing, and securing the entire Software Development Life Cycle.

MaintainAgent

Continuously monitors vulnerabilities, proposing self-repair strategies and enhancing system resilience.

ElicitAgent

Identifies inconsistencies, ambiguities, and gaps in requirements, ensuring clear and structured system specifications.

ArchitectureAgent

Translates system requirements into optimized architectural models, integrating design constraints and scalability factors.

TaskGenAgent

Breaks down specifications into prioritized, structured tasks, optimizing workflow distribution in agile development.

CodeGenAgent

Generates high-quality, standards-compliant code while collaborating with other agents for seamless development.

QualityAgent

Enforces software integrity through automated compliance checks, static analysis, and validation of design contracts.

DeploymentAgent

Optimizes CI/CD workflows by supporting deployment management, system logs analysis, and resource allocation.

TestGenAgent

Automates the generation of unit and integration tests, ensuring software reliability and alignment with requirements.

CITIZEN ENGAGEMENT

AI-assisted software development that enhances collaboration, decision-making, and smart city management.

HEALTHCARE & MEDICAL AI

Regulation-compliant, AI-powered software for precise patient care.

DISASTER RESPONSE & EMERGENCY MANAGEMENT

Intelligent tools for crisis response, resource allocation, and rapid decisions.

NEXT-GEN MANUFACTURING

AI-driven software for secure, high-performance industrial automation.

AUTOMATED MOBILITY

AI-powered code verification and self-repair for autonomous vehicle software.

The HIVEMIND responsible, human-centric AI framework ensures that software is built with four key characteristics:

COLLABORATIVE

SMART

RELIABLE

DYNAMIC